

COMPRESSION PROPERTIES OF SQUARE BRAIDED FABRIC -EFFECT OF LOADING CONDITION-

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ABSTRACT

Square braided fabric has been used as grand packing to keep out effluence of fluid. In case of applying square braided fabric to gland packing, compression properties are important. Cyclic compression test was performed on square braided fabric and the effects of compression speed were examined for aramid square braided fabrics. Moreover effect of impregnated with lubricant was investigated. From these results, deformation of compression with slowest compression speed was largest. It is considered that in rapid compression speed, the deformation of braided fabric might be generated only near surface.

1.INTRODUCTION

Braided fabric has a structure that exhibits the best of ability of fiber bundle, so that the composite with braided fabric has excellent mechanical properties. Representative braided fabrics are classified into three kinds of braided fabrics; flat braided fabrics, tubular braided fabrics and square braided fabrics, according to the shape and the manufacturing technique. The square braided fabric is shown in Fig.1, here, the fiber bundles are continuously oriented each other not only in plane but also through the thickness.

As an industrial product, square braided fabric has been used as grand packing to keep out effluence of fluid. In case of applying square braided fabric to gland packing, compression properties are important [1]. In order to clarify the fiber orientation state inside of the square braided fabric, sliced cross-section of the braided fabric was taken before and after compression. Thus, the fiber orientation state of the braided fabric was established. The effects of the type of fiber bundle, the number of fiber bundles, and the compression speed were also examined, and after compression strength of fiber bundle was investigated.

However, the effect of loading condition on the compression properties of braided fabric; there are boundary conditions, compression speed, and so on. Moreover, in actual application, square braided fabric is impregnated with lubricant. Therefore, the effect of lubricant on compression properties during cyclic loading test should be also investigated.

In this study, cyclic compression test of square braided fabric was conducted. Especially the effects of compression speed and impregnation with lubricant were investigated.

Fig.1 Square braided fabric

2.EXPERIMENT

2.1 FABRICATION OF SQUARE BRAIDED FABRIC

The schematic drawing of pass of fiber bundle of braided fabric is shown in Fig.2 (a). Arrows in this figure indicate the direction of the movement of the spindles. 4 tracks (track a, b) constructs 2 different fiber bundle passes as shown in Fig.2 (b); fiber bundle 'a' and 'b'. In Fig.2 (b), narrow and

wide lines show the outline of square braided and the fiber bundle passes respectively. The fiber bundle 'a' is composed by 2 straight lines connecting the corners diagonally and shows reciprocating motion. On the other hand, fiber bundle 'b' is composed by 4 straight lines connecting the 4 flat surfaces and shows round motion.

Fig.3 Compression method

Fiber bundles used in this study were aramid fiber bundle (HM-1055-7250d; AKZO). Moreover square braided fabric was impregnated with paraffin as lubricant. The compression and reconstruction properties of impregnated braided fabric were compared with non-impregnated braided fabric. In this study, non-impregnated braided fabric is called dry type and braided fabric with impregnated lubricant is called wet type.

2.3 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Cyclic compression test of square braided fabric was performed by Instron universal testing machine (Type4206). In the compression test, braided fabric was compressed between two flat platters and the side face was not constrained, as shown Fig.3. Square braided fabric for the test was 100mm in length. The specimen was compressed and unloaded between 2000N and 0N for 50 cycles. Cross head speed are changed at 1, 10 and 25mm/min. The hysteresis loop in load and displacement was measured.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In cyclic compression test of square braided fabric of dry type, hysteresis loops in load and displacement in speed 1mm/min, 10mm/min and 25 mm/min were shown in Fig.4 (a)(b)(c). In the loading cycle at the beginning the load increased gradually. And after approximately 2mm displacement, load increased rapidly. In reconstruction curve the load rapidly decreased. After 2nd compression cycle, region at which load gradually increased is small; there is only region at which load rapidly increased.

Fig.4 Hysteresis loops in load and displacement of dry type

Fig.2 Path of fiber bundle a and b.

From the results, the relationship between height of dry type specimen and the compression cycle was drawn. Fig.5 is the schematic drawing of 1st compression hysteresis loops in load and displacement. X-coordinate at Maximum load is defined as X_{max} and X-coordinate at minimum load

of reconstruction curve is X_{min} . Initial height is H_0 . H_0 minus X_{min} is compression height; H_0 minus X_{min} is reconstruction height. Fig.6 shows the compression cycle. In compression speed 1mm/min was lowest of three. In compression speed 1mm/min was the largest of three. In compression speed 1mm/min was the lowest of three.

Fig.5 the schematic drawing of 1st compression hysteresis loops in load and displacement

In compression test of wet type square braided fabric, hysteresis loops in load and displacement for compression speed 1mm/min, 10mm/min and 25 mm/min were shown in Fig 7 (a)(b)(c). Fig.8 shows the relationship between height of wet type specimen and the compression cycle. In compression test of wet type, at compression the height of compression speed 1mm/min was the lowest of three. In other words, the deformation of compression speed 1mm/min was largest of three.

Fig.7 Hysteresis loops in load and displacement of wet type

From these results, result of wet type compression test was similarly to result of dry type compression test. It should be said that the effect of lubricant was small in this material system. Also, deformation with slowest compression speed of 1mm/min was the highest of three. In slowest compression speed, compressive force was transmitted into inside of braided fabric, on the other hand in rapid compression speed, compressive force was not sufficiently transmitted into inside of braided fabric. It is considered that in rapid compression speed, the deformation of braided fabric might be generated only near surface.

This phenomenon is caused by heterogeneity of aggregation of fiber bundles. Most of researchers have been investigating visco-elastic properties of fiber bundles for the dependence of deformation speed on the deformation states. However according to our previous results that were conducted by precious observation of the fiber bundles it was cleared that the heterogeneity should be considered. Our next step for the effects of compression speed and lubricant was to conduct similar observations.

4.CONCLUSION

~~Fig.8 relationship between height of wet type specimen and the compression cycle~~
In this study, compression properties of aramid square braided fabric by changing compression speed were examined. Relationship between the compression speed and deformation were researched. If compression speed was rapid, deformation of square braided fabric was large. In slowest compression speed, compressive force was transmitted into inside of braided fabric, on the other hand in rapid compression speed, compressive force was not sufficiently transmitted into inside of braided fabric.

REFERENCES

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